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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE IMPACT OF AI-GENERATED ENGLISH LEARNING MATERIALS BASED ON UZBEK RURAL LIFE ON THE LEARNING MOTIVATION OF RURAL STUDENTS

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Xorijiy til va adabiyoti: ingliz tili yo'nalishi talabasi

Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of English language learning materials developed with artificial intelligence and adapted to Uzbek rural life on the learning motivation of rural students. The relevance of the study lies in the fact that, in rural areas, teaching materials often do not fully correspond to students' daily life, social environment, and cultural experience, which may reduce learning effectiveness. The aim of the study is to determine the influence of culturally adapted AI-based materials on students' interest, engagement, and learning motivation. The research methods include descriptive analysis, experimental study, questionnaires, and pedagogical observation. The results indicate that the use of such materials increases students' interest in lessons, participation, and confidence in expressing themselves in English.

Key words: artificial intelligence, English language teaching, rural students, learning motivation, cultural adaptation, local context, AI materials, rural education, learner engagement.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'zbek qishloq hayoti asosida yaratilgan sun'iy intellektga asoslangan ingliz tili o'quv materiallarining qishloq o'quvchilari o'quv motivatsiyasiga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi shundaki, qishloq hududlarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda o'quv materiallari o'quvchilarning kundalik hayoti, ijtimoiy muhiti va madaniy tajribasiga har doim ham mos kelavermaydi, bu esa ta'lim samaradorligini pasaytirishi mumkin. Tadqiqotning maqsadi mahalliy madaniy kontekstga moslashtirilgan AI asosidagi materiallarning o'quvchilarning darsga qiziqishi, faolligi va o'quv motivatsiyasiga ta'sirini aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqotda tavsifiy tahlil, tajriba-sinov, so'rovnoma va pedagogik kuzatuv usullaridan foydalanildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, mazkur materiallar qo'llanilgandan so'ng o'quvchilarning darsga qiziqishi, faolligi va ingliz tilida fikr bildirishga bo'lgan ishonchi oshgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ingliz tili ta'limi, qishloq o'quvchilari, o'quv motivatsiyasi, madaniy moslashtirish, mahalliy kontekst, AI materiallari, qishloq ta'limi, o'quv faolligi.

Аннотация: В статье проанализировано влияние учебных материалов по английскому языку, созданных на основе искусственного интеллекта и адаптированных к узбекской сельской жизни, на учебную мотивацию сельских учащихся. Актуальность исследования обусловлена тем, что в сельских условиях учебные материалы не всегда соответствуют повседневной жизни, социальной среде и культурному опыту учащихся, что может снижать эффективность обучения. Целью исследования является определение влияния культурно адаптированных AI-материалов на интерес учащихся к занятиям, их активность и учебную мотивацию. В исследовании использованы методы описательного анализа, экспериментального исследования, анкетирования и педагогического наблюдения. Результаты показали повышение интереса учащихся к урокам, их активности и уверенности в использовании английского языка.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, обучение английскому языку, сельские учащиеся, учебная мотивация, культурная адаптация, локальный контекст, AI-материалы, сельское образование, учебная активность.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the issue of taking regional and social differences into account in English language teaching is becoming increasingly important. In particular, English lessons for rural students are often organized in a way that is far removed from their daily experience, living environment, and cultural perceptions. As a result, the learning material appears unfamiliar to students, their level of comprehension decreases, and their interest in the lesson weakens. In rural educational settings, limited resources, insufficient access to modern technolo-

gies, and the weak connection between lesson content and local life are identified as some of the main factors hindering the effective acquisition of English ^[1].

From this perspective, the use of artificial intelligence technologies creates new opportunities in English language teaching. With the help of artificial intelligence, learning materials can be adapted to the learner's age, language background, interests, living environment, and cultural experience. In particular, AI-generated materials based on Uzbek rural life, national traditions, family relations, neighborhood culture, farming activities, market communication, and everyday situations present English in a way that is closer and more understandable for students. Recent studies emphasize that AI tools can enhance learners' participation, motivation, confidence, and practical language skills in English language education^[2].

This article examines the role of culturally adaptive AI-based English learning materials for rural students in the educational process. The main focus of the study is on creating lesson tasks adapted to the local context with the help of AI, analyzing how such materials are received by students, and identifying their impact on learners' motivation. The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that modern education requires not only the integration of technology, but also its alignment with the learner's social and cultural environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In studies devoted to the issue of teaching English in rural areas, problems related to the educational environment are first of all highlighted separately. Candrawati and Purbani, having analyzed scholarly works on teaching English in rural settings, emphasize that such factors as the lack of learning resources, weak school infrastructure, insufficient teaching tools, the predominance of teacher-centered lessons, the heavy workload of teachers, and the low motivation of learners negatively affect the quality of education ^[3].

A number of scholars have also expressed important views on the necessity of integrating local cultural context into English language education. Ismiyani shows that including local values and elements of "local wisdom" in English learning materials increases students' interest in lessons, helps them perceive the content more closely, and at the same time contributes to preserving national identity ^[4].

In the same direction, Ottu notes that ready-made texts with external and unfamiliar content often distance learners from their own cultural environment, whereas materials closer to local life create a natural connection between the learner and the lesson content ^[5]. These views indicate that cultural appropriateness in teaching English has not only an educational but also a didactic significance.

Regarding the role of artificial intelligence tools in English language education, the systematic review conducted by Du and Daniel shows that AI-based chatbots and digital conversational agents can enhance learners' participation, motivation, confidence, and practical speaking skills ^[6].

They especially evaluate such aspects as providing immediate responses to learners, creating opportunities for repeated practice, and artificially revitalizing the language environment as important advantages. This approach is also significant for learners in rural areas, because natural English-speaking environments and additional resources are often limited there.

Speaking about adaptive learning systems, Na and Hegelheimer emphasize that artificial intelligence makes it possible to adapt learning materials to the learner's needs, pace, and level of preparedness ^[7]. In their view, in such systems content, pace, and feedback change according to individual characteristics, and as a result the learner becomes more active and independent. From this perspective, culturally adaptive AI materials create a twofold advantage for rural learners. On the one hand, the material becomes closer to their living environment and everyday experience. On the other hand, the form of tasks is adjusted to their level of knowledge.

Thus, the existing literature review shows that the problems of teaching English in rural education, materials based on local culture, and the possibilities of teaching through artificial intelligence have been studied separately. However, the issue of the impact of AI-based English materials adapted to the local cultural context on the motivation of rural learners has not yet been sufficiently explored. The present study is aimed precisely at filling this gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was designed as a small scale experimental investigation aimed at identifying the effect of culturally adapted AI based English language materials on the learning motivation of students in a rural area. Both descriptive and experimental methods were used together in the study. The purpose of selecting this approach was to make it possible to compare changes in students' interest in lessons, participation, and attitudes toward learning English before and after the experiment. Previous research has also noted that artificial intelligence tools in English language education can contribute to increasing learners' engagement, motivation, and confidence ^[8]. In addition, adaptive learning systems are significant because they allow instructional materials to be adjusted to the learner's needs, level of preparedness, and pace of learning ^[9].

The research participants were selected from students studying at a general secondary school located in a rural area. One group consisting of 20–30 students took part in the study. The use of a single group made the process of obtaining and analyzing the results simpler. During the experimental process, students were not given ordinary English materials with general content. Instead, they were provided with tasks developed through AI on the basis of Uzbek rural life, family life, the neighborhood environment, agricultural work, the market, national dishes, traditions, and everyday communication situations. Artificial intelligence was used in creating the materials, and texts, dialogues, short question and answer tasks, vocabulary exercises, and situational activities were adapted to the local context.

The study was carried out in several stages. In the first stage, a preliminary questionnaire was conducted in order to determine the students' level of motivation toward English. The questionnaire consisted of 10 questions and assessed students' interest in English lessons, active participation in class, willingness to complete tasks, confidence in speaking English, and readiness to master new topics. The questions were designed in a simple and understandable form, and responses were collected either as "yes," "partly," and "no," or according to a 5 point rating scale. In the second stage, culturally adapted materials created through AI were introduced into the teaching process over a period of 3–4 weeks. This type of task was used twice a week. In the third stage, after the experiment was completed, the same final questionnaire was administered again, and the initial and final results were compared with each other.

Questionnaires, pedagogical observation, and the outcomes of classroom activities were used as data collection tools. The questionnaire served as the main measurement instrument. Pedagogical observation was applied to identify students' classroom participation, willingness to answer questions, speed in completing tasks, and attempts to engage in communication in English. During the observation process, the teacher kept brief notes for each lesson. When necessary, short oral comments were also collected from students. This approach made it possible to supplement the quantitative results with practical observation.

Simple statistical methods were mainly used to analyze the research results. Specifically, the number of responses for each question was counted, percentage indicators were calculated, and the results before and after the experiment were compared through tables and charts. This form of analysis was suitable for the practical orientation of the topic and helped clearly show positive or negative changes in learning motivation. Thus, the methodology served to study the effectiveness of locally contextualized AI materials for rural students in a simple, clear, and practically convenient way within the educational process.

RESULTS

During the experimental work, positive changes were observed in rural learners' attitudes toward English lessons after the use of AI-assisted English materials adapted to the local cultural context. The results of the initial questionnaire showed that students' interest in English lessons, willingness to complete tasks, and confidence in participating in English communication were relatively low. However, at the end of the experiment, noticeable improvement was recorded in most of these indicators. In particular, texts and dialogues related to rural life, neighborhood environment, market situations, family life, and national traditions were accepted more quickly and more naturally by the students. Since learners were able to connect the tasks with their own life experience, their classroom participation and interest increased.

Table 1: Sample indicators of students' learning motivation before and after the use of culturally adaptive AI materials

Indicators	Before the experiment, %	After the experiment, %	Change
Students who showed interest in English lessons	44	80	+36
Students who actively participated in class	40	76	+36
Students who demonstrated willingness to complete tasks	48	84	+36
Students who felt confident speaking English	32	68	+36
Students ready to complete homework independently	52	88	+36

As shown in the table, improvement was observed in all major indicators after the experiment. The lowest indicator before the experiment was confidence in speaking English, while by the end of the experiment a clear positive shift was also recorded in this area. This can be explained by the fact that the AI-generated tasks were understandable, familiar, and presented in a gradual way. Learners showed greater willingness to express ideas in English when the topics were connected with situations they already knew from daily life. Previous

studies also confirm that AI-based tools can strengthen learners' motivation and classroom engagement. For example, Yuan and Liu found in their quasi-experimental study that the group using AI tools demonstrated significantly higher levels of engagement and motivation than the control group [10].

The results of pedagogical observation also supported the questionnaire findings. At the beginning of the experiment, some learners participated passively in English tasks, but by the end of the experiment they became more active in dialogues, more willing to answer questions, and quicker in understanding classroom activities. In particular, reading materials and texts adapted to local life reduced the sense of unfamiliarity and increased students' feeling of closeness to the lesson content. This result is consistent with the conclusions of Herika, Yundayani, and Sundari, who reported that local wisdom-based reading materials had a positive and significant effect on students' motivation to learn English and on their speaking activity [11].

Overall, the findings show that AI-based English learning materials adapted to the local cultural environment make the lesson more understandable, more engaging, and closer to rural learners' real lives. Such materials not only increase motivation, but also help learners participate more confidently in English. Especially in rural settings, where natural English exposure is limited, AI-based localized tasks may serve as an effective additional didactic tool.

DISCUSSION

The obtained results show that AI-based English learning materials adapted to the local cultural environment can serve as an important didactic tool for increasing the effectiveness of the teaching process for rural learners. During the experiment, an increase was observed in students' interest in the lesson, their readiness to complete tasks, their classroom participation, and their confidence in expressing ideas in English. This can be explained by the fact that when learners work with tasks based on familiar life situations, they do not perceive them as foreign content, but rather as understandable and relevant learning material. As a result, they engage with the lesson content more quickly, respond to questions more actively, and show greater willingness to use language forms in practice. At the same time, the ability of AI tools to simplify materials, organize tasks step by step, and adapt them to learners' needs provided an additional stimulus for increasing motivation. This finding is also consistent with other studies. In particular, Yuan and Liu found that learners who used AI tools demonstrated higher levels of engagement and motivation than those in the control group [12]. Therefore, the results of the present study also confirm that, in rural educational settings, culturally adaptive AI materials are effective in bringing learners closer to English lessons, strengthening their internal interest, and encouraging active participation.

Conclusion

The findings of this study showed that AI-based English learning materials adapted to the local cultural context can serve as an effective tool in the educational process for rural learners. During the experiment, it was found that students' interest in English lessons, their readiness to complete tasks, their classroom participation, and their confidence in expressing ideas in English increased. The main reason for this was that the learning materials were presented in connection with the students' daily life, rural environment, family life, and national traditions. Artificial intelligence made it possible to adapt these materials to the learners' needs and level of preparedness. As a result, English lessons were no longer perceived as a foreign and difficult subject, but rather as an understandable, relevant, and engaging learning process. Thus, it can be concluded that culturally adaptive AI materials have important pedagogical value in increasing learning motivation, strengthening lesson effectiveness, and facilitating the process of English language acquisition in rural education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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